

>><https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/rediscovered-medieval-manuscript-offers-new-twist-on-arthurian-legend-180978705/>

More Arthwyr Lies and Propaganda from the Smithsonian

Using Dark Age manuscripts to validate Romantic era concepts about the real Welsh/Cymru “British” histories, and continuing the Smithsonian coverup of the “King Arthur Conspiracy”

AND

A very short discourse on the leftist revisionist history agenda, as evidenced by the author’s short bio. Without presumption that the two are “in cahoots” but merely “on the same wave.”

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
September 2021

Lexington, KY

September 21, 2021

Re: Merlin the Magician, and the age of the real King Arthwyr period

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway

Dear Readers,

First, I must say that I'm a researcher in Kentucky both through the Hidden Kentucky Project (www.hiddendestinationsky.com) and Ancient Kentucke Historical Association¹. I have uncovered a real conspiracy to hide Cygnus and Lyra aligned mounds² on a top-secret Army base (Bluegrass Army Depot where they stored Vx gas, etc.)³, and keep from the public knowledge of the Broaddus Site c. 1100's⁴ (during Madoc era), and of the Nicotani⁵/Ft. Ancient

¹ "[Ancient Kentucke Incriptions: Prince Madoc: Fact or Fiction](#)," J. Michaels, 2004

² https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

³ <https://www.bluegrass.army.mil/BGAD/History.aspx> & <https://www.cma.army.mil/bluegrass/>

⁴ "Eastern Kentucky University conducted an archaeological field school at the Broaddus Site (15MA179). The Broaddus Site is a Late Prehistoric Fort Ancient village site that was first recorded by GeoMarine, Inc. in 1994 during a Phase I survey at the Blue Grass Army Depot in Madison County. (Waite and Ensor 1994). A mound, approximately 70 cm in height and 25 m diameter, is located at the site. After our two field schools we now know that the site is a circular village, with a cleared plaza area in the center of a dense midden ring. Five diagnostic projectile points found during Waite and Ensor's (1994) survey indicate a long utilization of the site. These points span from the Late Archaic, include the entire Woodland, and end with the Late Prehistoric Period. The majority of projectile points, however, are Late Prehistoric triangular points that place the site firmly in the Late Prehistoric period. Ceramics recovered both by Waite and Ensor and EKV's field schools are predominately shell tempered, indicating primarily a middle to late Fort Ancient occupation. Two out of three radiocarbon dates from EKV's field school date to the very early 1200s. The presence of the circular midden ring also places the site firmly in the middle Fort Ancient. In summary, the Broaddus Site is best understood as a medium size, early middle Fort Ancient (1200 to 1400 AD Elkhorn Phase) circular village in the southern Outer Bluegrass region," Two Seasons at the Broaddus Site (15MA179): A Middle Fort Ancient Village in Madison County, Kentucky, Carmean, 2003

<http://www.kyopa.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/Volume-10-Number-2-Winter-2003.pdf>

⁵ "The facts, though few, are interesting. The order was hereditary; in this respect peculiar, for among Indians seldom, and among the Cherokees never, does power pertain to any family as a matter of right. Yet the family of the Nicotani--for it seems to have been a family or clan--enjoyed this privilege. The power that they exercised was not, however, political, nor does it appear that chiefs were elected from among them.

"The Nicotani were a mystical, religious body, of whom the people stood in great awe, and seem to have been somewhat like the Brahmins of India. By what means they attained their ascendancy, or how long it was maintained, can never be ascertained. Their extinction by massacre is nearly all that can be discovered concerning them. They became haughty, insolent, overbearing, and licentious to an intolerable degree. Relying on their hereditary privileges and the strange awe which they inspired, they did not hesitate by fraud or violence to rend asunder the tender relations of husband and wife when a beautiful woman excited their passions. The people long brooded in silence over the oppressions and outrages of this high caste, whom they deeply hated but greatly feared. At length a daring young man, a member of an influential family, organized a conspiracy among the people for the massacre of the priesthood. The

“Welsh Indians.”⁶ At that time, Kithiki (means land of meadows) was controlled by a powerful mixed clan of “priestly hereditary lords” and remaining Hopewell or Allegwian peoples. These people were familiar with the real King Arthwyr, who was King Arthur II according to the research of Wilson & Blackett,⁷ who managed to find the headstone of “REX ARTORIVS”^{8 9} at a predicted location, and documented with news cameras.¹⁰ So far they have never received permission to excavate the church on grounds where they maintain his remains will be found. Separately, R. MacCann of Oxford University has confirmed also that Arthur died in the Ohio River valley.¹¹ Both of these independent groups of researchers disagree with the origin - north or south Wales - but agree he died in the ORV, and therefore that Anfwynn (Otherworld) is Kithiki. They also agree that he was pre 5th Century.

Nevertheless, the real King Arthur Conspiracy is that these runic stones are spread out in Kithiki¹² and the governments of Britain, and Wales (Cardiff), and America have known about it. Setting that aside, the British Archaeological establishment does know that there are, in fact, 5th - 6th Century stones in Wales, scattered throughout, with references to King Arthur. In fact LiDAR of the Caer Melyn is not made available so that AKHA paid to have a drone fly over the site and catalog it.

This, and the facts of the ancient Llandaff Charters¹³, which have the family tree in inscriptions (as land contracts notarized by the church) in the margins of the ancient Bible which is established as pre-Romantic.¹⁴ It is certainly older than 800 years.

So how the Smithsonian, an organization that seems to have been caught destroying or at least covering up “giant” skeletons¹⁵ (7’ or so) from the Falls of the Ohio and “Lost City of Russellville”^{16 17} among others, and possibly helping to destroy the forts at O’Bynum and

immediate provocation was the abduction of the wife of the young leader of the conspiracy. His wife was remarkable for her beauty, and was forcibly abducted and violated by one of the Nicotani while he was absent on the chase. On his return he found no difficulty in exciting in others the resentment which he himself experienced. So many had suffered in the same way, so many feared that they might be made to suffer, that nothing was wanted but a leader. A leader appearing in the person of the young brave whom we have named, the people rose under his direction and killed every Nicotani, young and old. Thus perished a hereditary secret society, since which time no hereditary privileges have been tolerated among the Cherokees.” <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc108.htm>

⁶ “[Footprints of the Welsh Indians](#),” W. Traxel, 2004

⁷ “[Artorius Rex Discovered](#),” Wilson & Blackett, 1986

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H5mXbMxZWz0>

⁹ “[The Holy Kingdom](#),” A. Gilbert, 1998

¹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UxN1EaNxx30>

¹¹ “[King Arthur's Voyage to the Otherworld: Was Arthur killed in America?](#),” R. MacCann, 2016

¹² “King Arthur Conspiracy,” Wilson & Blackett, 2008

¹³ <https://www.library.wales/discover/digital-gallery/manuscripts/the-middle-ages/the-book-of-llandaff>

¹⁴ “[The Llandaff Charters](#),” W. Davies, 1979

¹⁵ <https://www.gaia.com/article/this-conspiracy-claims-the-smithsonian-destroys-giant-skeletons>

¹⁶ https://www.academia.edu/49945915/Ramons_AKHA_Articles p.6

¹⁷ <https://heritage.ky.gov/Documents/TheArchaeologyofKYAnUpdateVol2.pdf>

Portsmouth Earthworks,¹⁸ is trusted to report on this new 13th century manual, is beyond me.

Rosenthal, David <ROSENTHD@si.edu>

Wed, May 23, 2018, 1:12 PM

 to me ▾

Dear Sir,

The accession number you refer to is correct and the material is here.

Feel free to contact me with more questions as I am happy to try to answer them.

Regards,

Dave

David Rosenthal

Collection Manager, Archaeology and Ethnology

Department of Anthropology

<http://anthropology.si.edu/cm/index.htm>

rosenthd@si.edu

SMITHSONIAN INSTITUTION

NATIONAL MUSEUM OF NATURAL HISTORY

Figure 1 - Email about Fawn Hoof Mummy coverup; credit: author

Furthermore, I have spoken to the Smithsonian via email and confirmed, they do indeed have the Fawn Hoof mummy¹⁹. Moreover the Webb Museum²⁰ on Virginia Ave., Lexington, KY has two mummies with red hair which they will not allow me to see, even before the mysterious shakeup of the entire archaeological department there²¹!

There are 16 or so buried stone mounds in Yatesville Lake, KY which have never been excavated, and the entire Spratt Site, which I have personally verified is intact (as far as mounds are concerned) was refused to be excavated or documented officially, though the AKHA provided a site survey for free to KY State Archaeology ~1990. I am including some of the diagrams of this survey as proof.

¹⁸ <https://www.wdl.org/en/item/4301/>

¹⁹ "Hi David,

I am trying to confirm this information. Christina says that you are the person to confirm it.

"After 1876, it was turned over to the Smithsonian Institution. Eventually it was dismembered and the bones stored in a box under accession number 4789. Researcher Angelo George claims in his book (Angelo I. George, Mummies, Catacombs, and Mammoth Cave, George Publishing Company, 1994) that "Fawn Hoof is still doing well at her old box number in the Smithsonian," a silent reminder of her earlier celebrity life and of her connection to Mariettan Nahum Ward. "" ~Sf. Careaga

²⁰ <https://anthropology.as.uky.edu/museum-anthropology>

²¹ <https://www.kentucky.com/opinion/op-ed/article227843214.html>

Figure 2 - Spratt Site Survey; credit: AKHA

Figure 3 - Planet Venus "comet" (serpent) motif, as "nutting holes", Spratt Site

Figure 4 - Plasmascripts at Spratt Site (destroyed)

Figure 5 - Remains of ancient stone wall or cairn

SPRATT SITE, CLIFTON CREEK, MENIFEE COUNTY, KENTUCKY

(C) 1994 Lee Pennington

CODE FOR FINDS AT SPRATT PLACE

1. Verne & Ida Mae Spratt House
2. Original Archaeology site with snake wall, snake head in rockhouse, 23 plus stone mounds.
3. Snake wall, stone mounds, snake effigy in rockhouse, trident-awenturkey track on small rock down from rockhouse, dirt mound.
4. Indian Smoke Chimney, caves in cliff, some petroglyphs on rocks down from cliff, old claymine.
5. 2500' to 3000' long Archaeology site with snake wall broken in places perhaps from past timbering roads, 73 plus mounds (located at either end of wall) with largest number at west end.
6. Rockhouse with strange fill dirt (several tons brought in apparently).
7. The Sinks (40 plus acres), old coalmine at upper end.
8. Rockhouse with initials (reportedly Swift), date 1767 on wall .
9. Rockhouse with running man petroglyphs, (left-hand petroglyph and arrow destroyed), nutting holes in form of snake.
10. Large rockhouse, several nutting holes, place reported that box with golden calf retrieved, Buffalo Rock is nearby.
11. Large rockhouse with initials, the word MIKE or MINE, circles on wall, nutting holes; site has been worked with backhoe.
12. Direction of Wynn Hollow where large stone has several circle crosses and other symbols, turkey track; stone beside larger one apparently covered with tiny writing on one face; odd looking stone (Earth Mother?). Hollow below this area (before Dock Hollow) reportedly had vault opened that contained English crowns.
13. Direction of Devil's Marketplace; on ridge is Spratt's Turtle Back Rock, nearby stone with circle cross. Out ridge is hole in rocks where one can see the sky; smelting furnace reportedly found in first hollow east from Marketplace, waterfalls at head of Long Branch.

Figure 6

Figure 8

Figure 9 - More plasmascripts, now presumed destroyed

Figure 10 - Also destroyed

Now, looking at this article, I want to spend some time replying to some of the factless, and semi-Romanticised facets of the article, written by such a dubious source and questionably motivated author from a leftist/revisionist background. If they choose to respond, then they must first then acknowledge the Broaddus Site, and they will be loathe to do this, so I will not expect a real rebuttal but some form of self-confirming claims of “nutter” or “tin foil hat” or “bunk” which ignores the real LiDAR and Sat photos, as well as images of stones and established Cherokee myths cited herein and elsewhere.

Much of Arthurology is full of bunkish ideas about Arthur being from Lloegres (England) so this cannot be helped. Except we are dealing with established runic stones pre-dating the articles' claims, as well as cross cultural plasmaglyphic confirmation that Coelbren is real²², because its thematics predate Iolo Morganwygg and are in Chinese plasmaglyphics from the Shang era! These runes are found in Kentucky only in the Ft. Ancient region, not the Mississippian Region^{23, 24}.

²² https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

²³

<https://www.google.com/maps/@35.445984,-90.6229876,5z/data=!3m1!4b1!4m2!6m1!1s10CK4UUKBI4urcvV5bPAiYjqb3K0>

²⁴

<https://www.google.com/maps/@24.6672181,-68.6789241,3z/data=!3m1!4b1!4m2!6m1!1s18UNsi1tsmdbI3MqMFIWQKYtsHzwWTQDA>

The Article

“The 13th-century pages, found by chance at a British library, show a different side of Merlin, the magician who advised Camelot’s king”

Again this would be fully 1,000 years after Arthwyr, or Arthur II, ~330 AD, who died in Anfwynn (Avalon) according to Welsh lore. However, it is likely that Merlin Elwyg was either earlier, or not a magician but an advisor (as said) in druidism. But most commonly the stories in the romantics are actually Myrddin Wylt (Martin the Wild), from North Brython who plays the role of bard (magician).²⁵

“Thirteenth-century manuscript fragments discovered by chance at a library in Bristol, England, have revealed an alternative version of the story of [Merlin](#), the famed wizard of [Arthurian legend](#). A team of scholars translated the writings, known as the [Bristol Merlin](#), from Old French to English and traced the pages’ medieval origins,”

The French accounts come from old British/Cymru Normandy, and are always fragmented. They are inherited to begin with.

“The manuscript is part of a group of texts called the [Vulgate Cycle](#), or the Lancelot-Grail Cycle.”

Again, both of which are not real aspects of the Arthwyr legend, but Renaissance additions which became highly romanticized later. Lancelot was not a real character but a Christian archetype. A second (or third) Christ, in warrior form. Propaganda. The Holy Grail is real, we think, but had nothing to do with Arthwyr’s trip to Anfwynn. According to the stones, it was to flee the “plague” or rather a great conflagration seen even in Normandy after the electrocomet which may have also struck Peru/titicaca²⁶ passed over Glamorgan and set it afire, vitrifying castles²⁷.

They struck out straight across the Atlantic and passed into the St. Lawrence river, as MacCann notes²⁸, all the signs of Montreal’s geography are listed, as well as flora and fauna found in Otherworld.

²⁵

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hi_ll_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

²⁶ There is a 200-300 year dating discrepancy, some say 530-560 AD. Also the 30 year gap is thought to be a matter of when year 0 is to ancient vs. modern Christians (birth or death of Christ)

²⁷ <https://echoesinthemist.com/2012/06/23/vitrified-forts-of-scotland/>

²⁸ Which is different than Madoc, who came up the Miss. River with about 700 ships in might and power. They seized the “four rivers” and did not lose control until the Cahokians had the aid of Zheng He in the 1440s. It still took an alliance of all the Ani Kwitangi, Chinese, and Ameroindian tribes to wipe out the 3,000-6,000 Padoucans.

“James Wafford, of the western Cherokee, who was born in Georgia in 1806, says that his grandmother, who must have been born about the middle of the last century, told him that she had heard from the old people that long before her time a party of giants had come once to visit the Cherokee. They were nearly twice as tall as common men, and had their eyes set slanting in their heads, so that the Cherokee called them Tsunil’kälû’, “The Slant-eyed people,” because they looked like the giant hunter Tsul’kälû’ (see the story). They said that these giants lived very far away in the direction in which the sun goes down. The Cherokee received them as friends, and they stayed some time, and then returned to their home in the west. The story may be a distorted historical tradition.”

<https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc106.htm>

“The medieval Arthurian legends were a bit like the Marvel Universe, in that they constituted a coherent fictional world that had certain rules and a set of well-known characters who appeared and interacted with each other in multiple different stories,” [Laura Chuhan Campbell](#), a medieval language scholar at Durham University, tells [Gizmodo](#)’s Isaac Schultz. *“This fragment comes from the second volume, which documents the rise of Merlin as Arthur’s advisor, and Arthur’s turbulent early years as king.”*

This is breathtaking propaganda. At first we take something that is truly fictional, the romantics, combine with something that is real, the manuscript, and then brush it all aside as fictional by proxy. This is the British state policy since the 1800s when the Welsh were quelled and their language and writing forbidden to them²⁹, and Iolo branded a liar and inventor of language. He and, conveniently enough, the Cherokee are the only ones to invent whole languages and writing systems, and in the 1800s. If they are able to make a coherent language, they’d be the first in history to do so alone. No single linguist will support such a theory. J.R.R. Tolkien would absolutely not have supported this point of view.

“King Arthur first appeared in a history of Britain written in 829 or 830, notes the [British Library](#). That text describes him as a warlord or Christian soldier. Later accounts from the 12th century added new elements to the legend, such as Merlin’s mentorship of Arthur. English writer [Thomas Malory](#) compiled one of the best-known collections of the stories, [Le Morte d’Arthur](#), in the 15th century.”

This is, as has been remarked, patently false history. Furthermore, it’s “A History of Britain”³⁰ which was must have also been an ancient manuscript. It’s a very subtle way of mingling the idea that he first appeared in 830 AD. That’s 500 years after Arthwyr.

“Merlin’s image has changed dramatically over the centuries. In more modern versions of the King Arthur legends, he is a wise advisor to the king. In the earliest iterations of the story, however, Campbell says he was a “morally dubious” magical seer or even a “creepy little boy [whose] father is a devil.”

Again, they are speaking of Martin the Wild.

Much of this article is a mere recounting of the academic research in the Vulgate Cycle. I doubt very much that L. Gershon is herself implicated in a conspiracy to hide something that she doesn’t have firsthand knowledge. What interests me though is her Bio

“Livia Gershon is a daily correspondent for Smithsonian. She is also a freelance journalist based in New Hampshire. She has written for JSTOR Daily, the Daily Beast, the Boston Globe, HuffPost and Vice, among others.”

²⁹ <https://reconstructingourselves.wordpress.com/tag/baram-blackett-alan-wilson/>

³⁰ https://englisholymp.weebly.com/uploads/4/3/9/3/43938723/a_history_of_britain.pdf

Setting aside JSTOR, the last four of these publications are leftist rags, engaged in wild reimaginings of real white European history^{31 32 33}, in some kind of mad attempt to rectify the present through Orwellian retelling of the past.³⁴ And rags like HuffPo enforce this agenda at the point of leftist agenda and attacking the reputations and careers³⁵ of any who disagree with the historical revisionism or promote transparency.^{36 37} The most egregious thus far has been the 1619 Project^{38, 39} but it is not unthinkable that such organizations, and those that think like the leftist Social-deconstructionists⁴⁰, might want to dismantle the imagery of either King Arthur or Merlin.

It's a strange way to end the article. It is almost like taking a stab directly at Tolkien's Gandalf or more cogently and modernly (and less sacrosanct), Rowling's "Dumbledore"⁴¹, who despite being gay by retcon⁴², has not stopped the progressive mob from shame slamming J.K. Rowling.⁴³

I suspect, however, the greater damage and propaganda from the part of the Smithsonian, who are undoubtedly aware of the works of Wilson, Blackett, and Oxford's MacCann. They just don't care. At one point the Smithsonian was headed by a President who had never even heard of the Adena or Hopewell - the Allegwians.⁴⁴ It is unclear, except by government mandate (starting with Thomas Jefferson, if we are to trust R. Osman's hypothesis⁴⁵), why this coverup should continue. It has resulted in the dismantling of many stone forts, including Berea's Indianfort, and Charlestown State Park's "Devil's Backbone" fort, whose stone was used at excessive cost to build the "Big Four" bridge⁴⁶. Accounts by the French place the cairn mound of the Padoucan warriors slain at Corn and Sand Island as exactly where the

³¹ <https://www.amren.com/news/2017/05/nell-irvin-painter-the-history-of-white-people/>

³² <https://www.nationalreview.com/2019/03/destroying-history-confederate-statues-christopher-columbus/>

³³ "The Uniqueness of Western Civilization," R. Duchesne, 2011

³⁴

<https://www.returnofkings.com/183485/dont-believe-the-historical-revisionism-that-hollywood-inserts-into-world-war-ii-movies>

³⁵

<http://christiansfortruth.com/canadian-professor-fired-for-defending-uniqueness-of-white-european-civilization>

³⁶

https://www.huffpost.com/entry/ricardo-duchesne-white-nationalist-unb_n_5cdec3c8e4b09e057802c216

³⁷ For an older textbook not filled with political correctness, see

<https://archive.org/details/OxfordHistoryOfTheAmericanPeople>

³⁸ <https://www.independentsentinel.com/nyt-covered-up-massive-lie-about-the-1619-project/>

³⁹ https://www.americanthinker.com/articles/2019/08/the_lies_of_the_1619_project.html

⁴⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=el6TVEMnS3E>

⁴¹ <https://www.thethings.com/15-reasons-why-we-hate-dumbledore/> and

<https://www.quotev.com/story/13744064/Reasons-to-Hate-Dumbledore>

⁴²

<https://pjmedia.com/culture/tyler-o-neil/2018/02/01/latest-sjw-meltdown-dumbledore-wont-be-gay-enough-in-harry-potter-spinoff-n170694>

⁴³

<https://www.objectivist.co/2020/06/leftists-pile-on-harry-potter-author-j-k-rowling-for-speaking-truth-on-biological-difference-between-men-and-women/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jzaqM42cZe8>

⁴⁵ "Graves of the Golden Bear," R. Osman, 2011

⁴⁶ <https://apalacheresearch.com/2019/06/26/the-devils-backbone-charlestown-indiana/>

modern Falls of the Ohio State Park visitor center is located now⁴⁷. In that visitor center they are busy removing anything not P.C. enough for the progressive left, let alone refusing to tell the story of the genocide of the Nicotani even though it is Native history!^{48 49} To see anything like this, the only choice is a visit to the small, remote museum of Brandenburg⁵⁰ where the actual Brandenburg stone⁵¹ has finally made its way home, after being in Indiana for some time and then, due to mainstream pressures, removed and hidden from the public.

Was this mainstream archaeology, government, Native American progressives, or a combination thereof? I have no idea. But the result was a thorough shaming of the stone⁵². Many of the runic stones are missing. It is presumed that the Webb Museum is hiding - in a

Commonwealth - the Chi Roh stone⁵³ and Gaitskill Tablets both. Most of the Spratt runes have been destroyed due to [wanton] lack of protection⁵⁴. However, in Wilson and Blackett's book, "King Arthur Conspiracy," they document the actual discovery behind vines of Coelbren runes, and immediate translation⁵⁵, which I will reproduce here.

Figure 11 - Brandenburg Stone

⁴⁷ According to early accounts in Rafinesque regarding the first meetings of the Filson Historical Society
⁴⁸ https://www.stcharlesschoolsc.org/cms/lib/CA02223381/Centricity/Domain/148/tecumseh_speech.pdf

⁴⁹ "The prophet also claimed that the Creator had showed him the origin of white Americans. Unlike the Shawnees, the offspring of the Creator, Americans sprang from the Great Serpent of the Atlantic Ocean. Crawling onto the shores of North America, they first looked like giant crabs and settled in what is now Boston. Tenskwatawa exempted certain Europeans, including British, French, and Spanish, from this creation story, for they were also the offspring of the Creator and, therefore, brothers to the Shawnees. But he forbade any Indian to have contact with the Americans, because they were evil. Indians should never trade with Americans nor have relationships of any kind with them. They had corrupted some Indians ("witches"), and those Indians must be killed." As one can see, racism was not confined to whites, but was shared alike with natives and other world peoples of the time.

<https://billofrightsinstitute.org/essays/tecumseh-and-the-prophet>

Tenskwatawa had actually predicted the return of a pan-Indian alliance, and that one had been a success before. This was a Shawnee mirror of the Cherokee myths.

⁵⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brandenburg_stone has all the hallmark signs of leftist revisionism; so see <https://subscriber.thenewsenrprise.com/content/legendary-stone-returning-meade-county>

"It is said to read in ancient Welsh: "Toward strength (to promote unity) divide the land we are spread over purely (justly) between offspring in wisdom," according to *The Courier-Journal*."

⁵¹ Ibid. pp. 429-430

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outline_of_forgery

It is NOT a forgery!

⁵³ Ibid. pp. 462

⁵⁴ By contrast, State Archeology *raped* the Russellville mounds and those where the Louisville International Airport is now located, among other sites of conical mounds. Others remain untouched, some for historical reasons - as many pioneers place cemeteries on them - and for unknown political reasons. The secret map is over 28,000 markers as of 2018.

⁵⁵ Ibid. pp. 403-409 Bar Creek Slab, Clay County, KY (not more than 30 miles from Manchester's Red Bird Stone and cave https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Red_Bird_River_Petroglyphs)

This last Figure 12 was the part of Spratt Site petroglyphs.

"From below/under, in a state of going down, in need/want, all the whole of what is outward it shall be a place revered, the ruler in god the power the end manifest."

More in KY are to be found. Reports have reached me of a mummy kept in a high ridge, not told to State Archeology for fear of desecration.

- *"You are the power to go towards"*
- *"Together to cry out to you the trinity that is enfolding us."*
- *"In acute (flash) flooding (this is) a holdfast."⁵⁶*
- *"In difficulty have faith."*
- *"(in the) military ruler."*
- *"Towards my reward (from) the warrior, the ruler, what exists, the ruler fine/subtle he is."*

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

⁵⁶ Wilson, being from Wales, could not have known that this area is actually the location of one of the most heavy annual rainfall in Kentucky. Flash floods are very common there. The river is near the cave. Interestingly enough, the Spratt Site is located in an unexplained sudden increase of rainfall up north of Frenchburg, KY